

FLIPPED CLASSROOM: A CONTEMPORARY VYGOTSKIAN APPROACH IN THE ERA OF TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, countries worldwide have been taking broad steps to lead educational reforms in their educational systems to prepare their learners for employment by teaching them the required skills that would enable them to apply these skills in real-world scenarios. Consequently, to achieve this ultimate goal, educators shifted their attention towards adopting the flipped classroom approach as an active learning approach, which has earned much attention from educators and practitioners around the world as it has been claimed that the flipped classroom can consolidate the students' deep learning and motivate and engage students with their learning when compared with other didactic learning approaches which are considered tedious and daunting for the learners. Due to that, this paper presents the theoretical and practical methods embedded in implementing the flipped classroom in English classes by providing an example of using the flipped classroom strategy to teach ESL creative writing innovatively.

KEYWORDS

Flipped Classrooms, ZPD, Scaffolding, ESL, Creative Writing, Technology

1. INTRODUCTION

The 21st century is characterised by being the century of openness and globalisation, where human beings who are living in this century are being exposed to radical transitions that have impacted many sectors, such as the economy, industry, health, and even education. Regarding education, these changes can be witnessed explicitly in the paradigm shift in both teachers' and learners' roles in the learning process. For example, in traditional classes; the teacher is following “I Do,” “We Do,” and “You Do” strategy as he or she stands in front of the class, presents the content using a whiteboard, and a mouth to keep up with his or her explanation while the students are acting as passive learners who listen to the teacher carefully, and take notes without making any effective contribution to the lesson. This teacher-centred approach, when it occurs regularly, would make learners frustrated and anxious as it would inhibit them from acquiring the skills and the capabilities connected to the given knowledge [1].

However, such learning cannot be carried on in the current era for two reasons. The first one is related to the transition from “education for life” to “lifelong learning” as learners should not be filled with knowledge throughout their whole lifetime; on the contrary, they should be able to analyze, look for and perceive information whenever it is needed as that would pave the way towards creating students who are creative, critical thinkers, active decision-makers, and problem solvers. This is supported by [2] who mentioned that lifelong learning could lead to the development of learners personally and professionally as future specialists at any time, from any place. The second one is related to the emergence of technology, which is known for its ability to solve many problems related to low motivation and lack of engagement [3] and its significance in

equipping the students of today who are digital natives with the indispensable aptitudes of the 21-century to meet the requirements of our changing world [4]. As a result, there has been a tendency towards thinking of innovative ways to engage learners, which shed light on applying student-centered approaches such as flipped classroom that is considered one of the active learning methods where learners become active ones who are leading their learning process in the presence of a teacher who is acting as a facilitator.

Consequently, this journal explains the meaning and importance of the flipped classroom as a teaching pedagogy supported by technology. Moreover, it will discuss the flipped classroom's close relation with social constructivism principles. After that, I will elaborate on the efficacy of the flipped classroom pedagogy, which will be critiqued in the classroom by providing examples from my writing class. Eventually, recommendations and suggestions will be demonstrated to ensure the flipped classroom's successful application in different educational contexts.

2. AN OVERVIEW OF THE FLIPPED CLASSROOM

The flipped classroom was initially introduced by two Chemistry teachers, Jonathan Bergmann and Aaron Sams, in 2007, who decided to use recorded videos to improve the caliber of teaching Chemistry, especially for absent students [5]. After its application by Sam and Bergmann, it became increasingly popular in many educational contexts worldwide. For example, in their research about flipped learning and its implementation, [6] found 39 blogs and online articles about the subject in addition to 11 websites which urge educators to apply the flipped classroom and provide them with resources that would ensure its successful application

As a contemporary learning approach, scholars have used different definitions to define it. For instance, [7] referred to the flipped classroom as a student-centred approach that has two parts: one of these parts is connected to collaborative activities that can be done inside the class, and the other part refers to individual activities which can be completed using technology outside the class. Besides, [8] defined it as a model that can prepare the students for the presented lesson by watching videos, listening to podcasts, and reading articles. Despite the comprehensive meanings which were used to present the flipped classroom, such definitions faced criticism. For example, [9] refuted defining the approach as they claim that it is not a defined model since it can be applied using different tools to meet the students' demands. Their opinions were advocated by [10], who argued that there is no unified meaning for the flipped classroom as each teacher around the globe has his or her unique teaching strategy, which would ensure the students' engagement.

However, one of the straightforward definitions of the flipped classroom is the one which was suggested by [11], as they refer to it as what is done in school is done at home, and what is done at home is done at school. Depending on this definition, [12] presented in their book (Flip your Classroom) an accessible application of the F.C. in which the students are asked to watch online videos at home that the instructor previously prepares while the students take notes and write questions about the complicated things [13]. Consequently, during the class, the students are asked to do activities, answer questions, make inferences, discuss important concepts, and solve problems [14]. Even this application encountered discord among researchers, as some of them referred to the FC without mentioning the role of video or technology [15]. However, to implement this approach successfully, the Flipped Learning Network [16] indicated four pillars that should be available in any flipped classroom, which were put together in the acronym (FLIP), which can be explained in the following points:

- 1- F refers to a flexible environment that is associated with the flexibility of the time and the place in which learning occurs.

- 2- L refers to the alteration of the learning concept that moved from teachers to students, as the latter are active learners who are responsible for their learning while the former's job is to guide on the side.
- 3- I refer to the choice of the content as the teacher has the option to opt which content should be taught in the class and which one should be pre-studied
- 4- P refers to the professional educator whose role is not solely to prepare elaborate videos or presentations; his responsibility widens to communicate with the learners, provide feedback, and assess them continuously.

Consequently, to implement the flipped classroom successfully, these pillars could be enhanced with the use of technology [17] that has impacted education by providing a wide range of materials such as YouTube, screencastify, flip grid, and Ed-Talk that educators can use in the FC to support their students' needs as they can practice their learning in real-life contexts [18].

In addition, in FC contexts, technology plays a significant role in increasing the collaboration between the learners themselves and their teachers as the advent of blogs, wiki-pages and podcasts alter the method in which learners can collaborate, making the learning an enjoyable experience which would enhance the learners' motivation and performance [19]. The technology could indeed foster the application of FC; nevertheless, some concerns are associated with it. Firstly, some teachers are not technology experts as they do not know how to create a video to be used as teaching material, or they may create materials that do not imply high thinking skills [20], which would deprive the learners of constructing the knowledge. Secondly, not all students possess smartphones or laptops; some suffer from internet connection issues, especially in impoverished areas [21].

When implemented successfully by combining the four pillars with technology, the FC can positively affect students and parents. One of these positives is to prepare the learners for the learning process [22] with great flexibility [23], where students would be able to learn things at their own pace at any time in any place [24]. The second advantage is related to its ability to foster the learners' engagement as it would enhance the students' participation [25] and focus in the class [26] using the complicated higher levels of thinking of Bloom's taxonomy [27]. Also, [28] suggested that the flipped classroom could benefit parents by keeping track of their children's performance and knowledge by following the contents of the different subjects their children are studying.

Despite the advantages of flipped classrooms, many researchers have stated significant disadvantages in some areas. The first area is related to the students' motivation since the successful implementation of the flipped classroom relies heavily on the students' motivation. The second area has to do with the lack of direct contact with the teachers as [29] stated that students would not be able to ask immediate questions to their teachers while they are watching the videos as some of them may forget the issue that used to trouble them when they come in the second day to the class.

3. THE THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE FLIPPED CLASSROOM BASED ON SOCIAL CONSTRUCTIVISM

Since the teaching practices that teachers are using are based on theories which are integral to education, it is essential to connect theories with teaching pedagogies as the comprehension of theories would enable educators "to reflect on the teaching practice, improve upon it, reshape it, filter their work, and contribute to accelerating the discipline" [30] (P.4). This is supported by [31], who went further in stating that understanding the learning theory would aid educators to

plan the lesson effectively and support it with teaching pedagogies to ensure the effectiveness of teaching. As a result, the flipped classroom will be connected with social constructivism as teachers today are using a myriad of active learning practices which are based on social constructivism principles in which students play an active role in the learning process as they are responsible for the knowledge construction through social interaction using social, cultural, and artefacts tools which would finally lead to the internalization of the action [32]. Additionally, [33] mentioned that social constructivism stresses the importance of language as the most critical artefact that would stimulate communication between peers, teachers, and other people in society, as the language would enable the learners to help each other and lead them to solve problems collaboratively. However, Vygotsky's theory has been criticised in three ways. Firstly, Vygotsky stresses the importance of group thinking and ignores learners' individuality [34]. Secondly, Vygotsky did not identify a precise meaning for social interaction [35]. Thirdly, many researchers criticized its heavy reliance on language as the primary tool for constructing knowledge [36]

Despite its unavoidable criticism, social constructivism did not lose its glamour as a critical learning theory that supports the flipped classroom pedagogy. Many researchers linked the flipped classroom to social constructivism [36],[37], [38], as these studies allowed the researchers to strengthen the link between flipped classrooms and Vygotsky's theory by referring to two points: the ZPD and scaffolding.

3.1. The Zone of Proximal Development

[39] defined the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) as “the distance between the actual development level as determined by independent problem solving and the level of potential development as determined through problem-solving under adult guidance or in collaboration with a more capable peer” (p.86). By referring to the definition, it can be understood how important is to have a competent person who could be the teacher or a peer during the learning process. The teacher's role is not only to check what the learners know; it goes beyond to check what the students are capable of knowing. Teachers can apply the ZPD concept by understanding the students' current knowledge and then creating a suitable environment to help them move to the next level by benefiting from another knowledgeable person's help [40]. The idea of the ZPD resonates well with the flipped classroom as the guidance and support are done twice: first, through the video prepared by the instructor, which is supposed to be watched by the learners at home, and second, through the collaborative interaction with peers in the class. When this interaction is done collaboratively through peers, the less knowledgeable students will move to the next level of the ZPD. In addition, the flipped classroom context allows the teacher to correct the students' misconceptions and help the struggling students by re-teaching them the complex concepts [41]. However, [42] were among the first researchers who criticised the ZPD as they stated that the ZPD concept's ambiguity did not consider the learners' learning needs, capabilities, or even their motivational impacts. Also, it did not provide any account of how the development happened. Even [43] went further as he suggested replacing the ZPD with the 'Intermental Development Zone' (IDZ), which shifts the role of the teacher from being a facilitator into a creator of a learning community which is based on inquiry where students can take an active, shared, and reflective responsibility of their comprehension which represents the core of the flipped classroom.

3.2. Scaffolding

Scaffolding is a term which Bruner coined- and then it was grounded later in social constructivism- which can be defined as “a metaphor which is used in teaching and learning to describe the system of temporary guidance offered to the learner by the teacher, jointly co-constructed and then removed when the learner no longer needs it” [44] (p.1). By referring to the

definition, it can be suggested that scaffolding is related to the help that the teacher is providing in order to aid the learners in completing the tasks on their own after being provided with all the possible tools, such as feedback, evaluation, and fading assistance [45] from the teacher's end or even a computer to help the learners to move to the next level unaided. As the teachers keep evaluating the students' progress and continue to provide consistent feedback to urge continuous development, they gradually fade the students' given help. [46] referred to the essential concept of fading when scaffolding, mentioning that scaffolding should not be provided whenever the learner no longer requires it. In the flipped classroom, the videos can utilize the teachers in the scaffolding process [47]; however, they should be clear and short since instructors could compress the contents which are used for instructions to reduce the amount of freedom and the needs of the taught subject [48]. As a result, using the flipped classroom would "free up class time, allowing more individual and small group instructions" [49] (p.5). The freeing up of time enables the teacher to help the learners complete the task. In addition, throughout the class activities, teachers can use tools that would increase the students' motivation to keep working on the task. Despite the essential role that scaffolding can play in supporting the learners, it was criticised for ignoring the teachers' and students' cultural differences [50]. Also, teachers are not sustained with definitive guidelines on how scaffolding could lead to successful results since it is treated as an umbrella that includes all kinds of support [51]. Besides, scaffolding always follows only one direction as it is done from proficient to beginner as it treats the learner as a passive one [52] who always depends on the support of others, which contradicts the essence of social constructivism, which views the learner as an active partner of the learning process.

4. FLIPPED CLASSROOM PRACTICES FROM MY ESL CLASSROOM

Teaching English has undergone many changes globally to create motivating and communicative environments for students. As an English teacher, I had to conform to these changes by significantly changing my planning, curriculum, and assessment. These changes were driven by the emergence of technology and accompanied by other uncontrolled situations, such as the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic.

In response to these changes, I started applying the flipped classroom in my classes, which became part of my virtual bag. It is true that the data regarding its effect in English is limited compared to other STEM subjects [53]; however, some studies presented its successful implementation in some areas of the language, such as its positive influence on enhancing academic writing [54] and reading comprehension [55].

To add a contribution to these studies, I opted to write about the application of the FC in writing since it is one of the most complex skills to teach and learn, and it is a very baffling task as it needs control over numerous sub-skills which are present in its process [56]. In this FC, my students were asked to write a spooky short story and convert it into a book using technology. To implement the FC, I used a very detailed lesson plan since Vygotsky (1978) stated the importance of planning, which is considered a metacognition process that should be prioritised as it can lead to self-regulated knowledge [57]. In my plan, I designed the lesson following the three stages of the FC suggested by [58]: the pre-class stage, the in-class activities, and the post-class activities (See Appendix A). In designing the plan, I identified my lesson's primary objective, which is to write a short story applying the elements of a narrative story. In this stage, planning this FC lesson was challenging since I needed to follow the revised model of the Blooms' taxonomy (See Appendix B), which made it a highly complex process, and it was time-consuming as considered by [59] as it needed lots of preparation from my end to achieve the desired results.

After planning the lesson, I started working on preparing a pre-class activity, creating a video that talks about the short story elements using the Ed-Puzzle platform (See Appendix C). Using the

video is essential as it “brings the world to the class, and they are appealing and engaging” [60]. When preparing the video, I aligned it with the framework suggested by [61], which indicated that the video should be short, on topic, and full of animation and humour to motivate the learners. This video is considered an essential aspect of social constructivism as it can be used as a mediated artefact leading to the learner's cognitive development [62]. Besides, the video is a successful scaffolding tool as it provides the students with the knowledge needed to work independently on the given tasks [63]. Despite the successful implementation of this stage, it has been noted that some students, especially the struggling ones, came to class without watching the video, which affected both the teacher and students as this would inhibit the former from continuing the lesson [64] while the latter would not be able to follow on with the class activities [65]. However, this problem has been solved by creating engaging and appealing videos for the students, provided with scaffolding tools such as captions and transcripts, as this was suggested by [66]

The second stage of my FC is linked to in-class activities. At the beginning of my class, I asked the students to do a multiple-choice quiz on Kahoot (See Appendix D), as this quiz is known for its ability to assess the learners' prior knowledge and reduce feelings of anxiety [86]. Moreover, it would enable the teacher to decide who needs extra support or scaffolding during the period. Since the video presented the short story elements, I started the lesson by giving them some instructions. I presented for them the online rubric which was created using <https://www.quickrubric.com/r#/create-a-rubric> (See Appendix E) as it would help them to evaluate their work and each other's [67]. The rest of the period was used to engage students in collaborative online activities using Google Classroom. The class was divided into groups of 6 students, as each group was given a story to read and analyse by identifying the story elements. As the learners were working together, they benefited from the explanatory talk and the dialogue with each other as these two tools allowed them to start a discussion, answer questions, assess each other's work using online tools and provide feedback, as these strategies would help them in constructing the knowledge. As a socio-constructivist teacher, my role in this stage was to facilitate the students' learning as I was roaming around the class, listening to the groups, managing the class, correcting misconceptions, and providing feedback which was a vital part of the learning process, since it is considered as one technique of scaffolding which would aid teachers and even expert peers to support the low performers to utilize them to do the task without help. The group work in the in-class activities was helpful as the students were engaged in the activity, which improved their communication skills [68]. Even the struggling and the introverted ones were responding positively to the support which their peers did in planning the short story; however, the group work here wasn't controlled perfectly due to the large number of students in the class, and unfortunately, some students could not perform the task despite the scaffolding which was done by either the teacher or the peers as researchers suggest that the assistance provided by peers during cooperative learning may not be sufficient for all the students, even some of them were dependent on the high performers to do for them the tasks [69]. This is compatible with the findings of [70] and [71], who suggested that the collaborative approaches can be practical when done either with a small group or peer support as they cannot be applied in large classrooms and even when they are used with small groups, since the effectiveness of its approaches cannot be guaranteed.

Moving to the third stage of the FC, the learners apply what they have learned in the class session by filling in their short stories' organisers using Google Docs (See Appendix F). As the students began writing, continuous feedback, whether a written one or through voice, was given to the students to ensure that their writing would meet the required standards which were mentioned in the rubric, which is considered as “ a pedagogy of contingency” [72] to ensure that learning is kept on the track as the use of rubrics has been proved for its ability to enhance the students' learning, motivation, and their study at large [73] (p.138). In addition, students were asked to

reflect upon their work using the personal reflection form (See Appendix G). Even at this stage, learners were allowed to assess each other's work by giving them the option of peer and group editing, which is vital in increasing their writing performance [74]. When the organizer has been approved, learners started writing their stories using Book Creator <https://bookcreator.com> (See Appendix H), which made the learners fully engaged with their stories. Nevertheless, two obstacles emerged in this stage as some students started complaining about the workload that they had to do in this stage, and even the parents became worried about the large amount of time that their children were spending using the technology to get the work done as this would lead to detrimental effects on their health. Activities were divided into small chunks to tackle these issues, and even the deadlines were so flexible that students could finish the post-class tasks at their own pace.

By referring to the three stages of the FC, I would say that the implementation of the FC was an effective pedagogy in allowing the learners to apply the complex writing strategies since it saved both my time and the students' time and allowed them to self-regulate their learning using technologically efficient tools. These advantages were confirmed by [75] and [76], who conducted studies about the efficiency of the FC in teaching writing.

5. CONCLUSION

The journal aims to evaluate the efficacy of using the flipped classroom in the light of social constructivism accompanied by technology. The assignment starts by introducing the concept of flipped classroom, which is an active learning methodology defined in different ways by different scholars. Referring to these definitions, it can be understood that there are no definitive definitions for the flipped classroom as they depend heavily on the teacher, the lesson, and even the authorities.

In the second part of the journal, a close relationship has been constructed between the FC and social constructivism depending on two areas which are related to scaffolding and ZPD as these two areas are linked to the FC application through collaborative work where learners are engaged in activities that would stimulate their social communication skills through using scaffolding tools which would enable them to construct the internalized knowledge.

In the third part, the application of the FC has been presented by referring to a writing lesson in an English classroom using the three stages of the FC; pre-class activities, in-class activities, and post-class activities by mentioning the technological tools and activities which were used, criticizing the arising problems that emerged out of the application, and giving some suggestions that were followed to tackle these issues. As the FC has been discussed, it becomes evident that authorities need to implement the FC in all the stages from K to university graduate by educating all the stakeholders of its beneficial effects on preparing responsible and autonomous learners who are equipped with the 21-century skills which would enable them to make influential and successful contributions in the community.

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APPENDIX A

Flipped Classroom Creative Writing Lesson Plan

Lesson Name: Creative Writing (Writing a Scary Story Using the Book Creator)	
Subject: English Language	
Date: 11/11/2019	Grade: 8

<p>Lesson Objectives: To write a narrative scary story by applying the elements of the narrative writing by integrating the technology.</p>
<p>Pre –Class Activities: Students watch a video which can be found on Ed-puzzle https://edpuzzle.com/media/606f22fc4e9f9b41a5fda981 about the elements in the story and answer the multiple choice questions which are related to the video</p>
<p>In Class Activities: (10 minutes) -Students are asked to do a Kahoot quiz https://create.kahoot.it/details/f38817a7-5c50-4b03-8508-231195aa9359 individually based on the video that they had watched.</p> <p>-(5 minutes) Students are divided into mixed ability groups out of six members. -(5 minutes) students are given instructions based on the task. -(5 minutes) students are given an explicit explanation of the writing rubrics. -(15 minutes) Each group is given a scary story to read as they need to work together to find the elements of the scary story by using the color coding. -(Throughout the whole period) Teacher provides help and scaffolding for the ones who need . -(5 Minutes) Groups are asked to reflect on their work. - (15 minutes) Students in each group are asked to exchange their read story with another group to provide feedback on each other’ work. --(5 Minutes) Groups are asked to reflect on other groups’ work.</p>
<p>Post Class Activities: - Students are asked collaboratively to fill the graphic organizer for their scary story by opening a breakout room using the Google Classroom Platform. https://classroom.google.com/u/1/h -Students provide an audio or written feedback on their work -Teacher checks the students’ work and send an audio feedback on the students’ work. -Students start writing the story using the book creator application as groups https://bookcreator.com . -Students provide a feedback on their written stories.</p>
<p>Assessment: -Teacher checks the students’ stories and their presentation using the rubric.</p>

APPENDIX B:

BLOOM'S TAXONOMY IN A FLIPPED CLASSROOM

Retrieved from: <https://accelerate.uofuhealth.utah.edu/explore/how-to-flip-your-classroom-or-meeting-to-achieve-meaningful-learning>

APPENDIX C:

Short Story Elements
Rasha Najeh

The video can be found at: edpuzzle.com/media/606f22fc4e9f9b41a5fda981

APPENDIX D:

Available at: <https://create.kahoot.it/details/f38817a7-5c50-4b03-8508-231195aa9359>

APPENDIX E:

Creative Writing Rubric

Creative Writing Rubric: Criteria for Grading Creative Writing
Please fill in the self-assessment section on the bottom before handing in this assignment

	A	B	C	D/F
Meaning/Content: the extent to which the assignment exhibits sound understanding/interpretation/analysis				
Story Structure	Establishes strong plot/setting/character/pt. of view	Establishes plot/setting/character/pt. of view	Some elements of story structure, title blending of dialogue and narration	Few/no story structure elements present
Characterization	Develops complex characters through dialogue, narration and action	Develops characters through dialogue, narration and action	Some character development	Characters are not developed
Development: the extent to which ideas are elaborated, using specific and relevant evidence				
Ideas	Develops ideas clearly and fully, uses a wide range of relevant details	Develops ideas clearly; uses relevant details	Develops ideas briefly; uses some detail	Uses incomplete or undeveloped details
Organization: the extent to which the assignment exhibits direction, shape, and coherence				
Designing Organization	Maintains a clear focus; exhibits a logical, coherent structure through approp. transitions	Maintains a clear focus; exhibits a logical sequence of ideas through appropriate transitions	Exhibits but does not always maintain an appropriate focus; some inconsistencies in sequence of ideas	Lacks an appropriate focus, but suggests some organization
Specific Assignment Directions	Exceeds all requirements specified for this assignment	Meets all requirements specified for this assignment	Meets some of the requirements specified for this assignment	Meets few/no requirements specified for this assignment
Language Use: the extent to which the assignment reveals an awareness of audience and purpose				
Description	Creative, concrete language; uses literary devices and rich sensory detail	Assignment uses concrete language, literary devices and sensory detail	Some use of concrete language, literary devices, and sensory detail in assignment	Little use of concrete language, literary devices or sensory detail in assignment
Word Choice	Uses sophisticated precise vocabulary	Effective word choices	Some effective word choices	Few effective word choices
Sentence Variety	Well-varied sentence structure throughout	Good sentence structure and variety	Occasional use of sentence variety	Little sentence variety
Voice/Tone of Audience	Unique voice; strong sense of audience	Exhibits awareness of voice and audience	Some awareness of voice and audience	Mechanical/unintelligible voice; unaware of aud.
Conventions: the extent to which the assignments exhibits conventional grammar/spelling/word usage				
Grammar/Punctuation	Smooth, fluid error-free punct./grammar	Mostly correct grammar; errors do not interfere with communication	Errors occasionally interfere with communication; such errors are	Grammatical errors are awkward and interfere with communication
Spelling and Word Usage	Correct spelling; error-free word usage	Mostly correct spelling and word usage	Errors in spelling and word usage	Mis spelled and misused words throughout
Overall assignment presentation	MLA heading; unique title; professional presentation	MLA heading; appropriate title; neat presentation	Incomplete heading; average title/presentation	No heading/title; no attention to presentation
Self-Assessment: The best aspect of this assignment is: _____				
One aspect of this assignment that may require further revision is: _____				
The grade I would give this assignment is: _____				

APPENDIX F

The Scary Story Graphic Organizer

Name _____

<p style="text-align: center;">Scary Setting</p> <p>Where _____</p> <p>When _____</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Characters</p> <p>Main _____</p> <p>Other _____</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Interesting Beginning (like "It was a dark, and stormy night," or ask "What if...")</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Problem (The scariest thing that happens)</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Event 1</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Event 2</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Event 3</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Solution</p>		

APPENDIX G: VARIOUS ASSESSMENTS

The Writing Rubric

CATEGORY	Exemplary	Proficient	Partially Proficient	Unsatisfactory	POINTS
Focus on the Task	3 points Stays on task all of the time without reminders.	2 points Stays on task most of the time. Group members can count on this person.	1 point Stays on task some of the time. Group members must sometimes remind this person to do the work.	0 points Hardly ever stays on task. Lets others do the work.	___/3
	A true team member who works hard and helps others in the group.	A strong group member who tries hard!	Sometimes an active group member, but needs to try harder.	Sometimes chooses not to help out, and does not complete tasks.	
Work Habits	3 points Is on time for meetings, turns in all work when it is due.	2 points Usually on time for meetings, turns in most work when it is due.	1 point Sometimes late for meetings, often turns in work late.	0 points Late for all or most meetings, and late turning in work.	___/3
	Completes assigned tasks and does not depend on others to do the work.	Completes most assigned tasks.	Does not follow through on most tasks and sometimes counts on others to do the work.	Does not complete tasks. Depends on others to do all of the work.	
Listening, Questioning and Discussing	3 points Respectfully listens, discusses, asks questions and helps direct the group in solving problems.	2 points Respectfully listens, discusses and asks questions.	1 point Has trouble listening with respect, and takes over discussions without letting other people have a turn.	0 points Does not listen with respect, argues with teammates, and does not consider other ideas. Blocks group from reaching agreement.	___/3
	Research and Information-Sharing	3 points Gathers information and shares useful ideas for discussions. All information fits the group's goals.	2 points Usually provides useful information and ideas for discussion.	1 point Sometimes provides useful information and ideas for discussion.	
Problem-Solving		3 points Actively seeks and suggests solutions to problems.	2 points Improves on solutions suggested by other group members.	1 point Does not offer solutions, but is willing to try solutions suggested by other group members.	0 points Does not try to solve problems or help others solve problems.
	Group/Partner Teamwork	3 points Works to complete all group goals.	2 points Usually helps to complete group goals.	1 point Occasionally helps to complete group goals.	0 points Does not work well with others and shows no interest in completing group goals.
Always has a positive attitude about the task(s) and the work of others.		Usually has a positive attitude about the task(s) and the work of others.	Sometimes makes fun of the task(s) or the work of other group members.	Often makes fun of others' work and has a negative attitude.	
All team members contributed equally to the finished project.		Assisted group/partner in the finished project.	Finished individual task but did not assist group/partner during the project.	Contributed little to the group effort during the project.	
Performed all duties of assigned team role and contributed knowledge, opinions, and skills to share with the team. Always did the assigned work.		Performed nearly all duties of assigned team role and contributed knowledge, opinions, and skills to share with the team. Completed most of the assigned work.	Performed a few duties of assigned team role and contributed a small amount of knowledge, opinions, and skills to share with the team. Completed some of the assigned work.	Did not perform any duties of assigned team role and did not contribute knowledge, opinions or skills to share with the team. Relied on others to do the work.	
TOTAL POINTS					___/18

Self-Assessment & Peer Assessment

Self-assessment Guide
Use this form to evaluate your own writing by completing each sentence below.

What I like best about this piece of writing is _____

When I look back at the project, the part I most enjoyed working on was _____

The most difficult part of the project was _____

I was most successful at _____

One thing I learned from this project was _____

I would assess my work on this project as (outstanding, good, fair, weak) _____

One thing I need to improve in my next writing project is _____

One goal I would like to focus on in the future is _____

Peer Response Guide
Use this form as you respond to the writing of a classmate.

What is best about this piece of writing? _____

Is the opening interesting and attention getting? What, if anything, could help make it more so? _____

What is the focus of this piece? Do all of the parts work to support the whole? _____

Would it be possible to organize the ideas or events more clearly? How? _____

Are the paragraphs and sentences clearly and logically connected? Where could transitions be introduced to make connections more clearly? _____

Has the writer told enough about each part of the subject? Where are more details needed? _____

Where is the language precise and vivid? Where is the language vague or confusing? _____

Where are there errors in usage, spelling, capitalization, or punctuation that need to be corrected? _____

APPENDIX H

Available at: <https://bookcreator.com/online>

A sample of a story created using the book creator application:

AUTHOR

Rasha Abdulraheem is a dedicated educator and quality assurance specialist with over 20 years of experience in school inspection, assessment leadership, and teacher training. She has two Master's degrees: leading teaching and learning from the University of Dundee and an MPhil in leadership and Management from UCAM. She is pursuing a doctorate at UCAM University, as her research focuses on empowering educational leaders to improve inspection outcomes through sustainability, innovative technology, and emerging pedagogical approaches, such as gamification, flipped classrooms, project-based learning (PBL), and AI in education. She is also deeply interested in how leadership practices can drive meaningful change in schools and ultimately enhance their performance. Moreover, Rasha is an adjunct leadership professor at the UOP.

During her career in the private sector and the Ministry of Education, she has guided numerous schools through NEASC and KHDA accreditation, ensuring alignment with international standards while elevating student success. As a certified educator who has obtained CELTA, PGCE, and AI Diploma, she leverages cutting-edge strategies to equip educators and foster engaging learning environments.